

Sexuality in Assamese Culture: An Analytical Study

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Abstract: *Sexuality is a natural and inborn characteristic of a human being. It represents the masculine or feminine physical characteristics of a person. The concept of sexuality includes aspects of a person's biological status, reproductive processes, reproductive organs, sexual characteristics of a person such as masculinity etc.. Sex is an integral part of human life. Sexual intercourse between a man and a woman produces child, reproduces and builds a society. Without sexual activity, humanity cannot exist. As social animals, humans reflect sexual attitudes through their various social customs or activities. Different thoughts and attitude towards sexuality are also reflected through cultural activities. This study attempts to determine the sexual attitude reflected in various aspects of Assamese culture. In this study, many aspects of Assamese culture that are analyzed by direct observation.*

Key word: *Sexuality, Assamese culture, culture of cultivation and sexual thoughts, Sexuality and religion, Sexuality in festivals.*

I. Introduction

Assamese culture is a part of the Indian culture. Assamese culture does not refer to the culture of any particular nation or ethnic group; rather than, it is a culture of harmony influenced by Aryans and non-Aryans. There are many different ethnic groups that have arrived in Assam at different times and have settled in this territory. In this regard, the Assamese culture has elements of various ethnic groups such as Negrito (Negro), Austrian, Mongolian, Dravidian, Aryan etc. Moreover, the civilization and culture of Assam is mainly dependent on cultivations due to its favorable climate. Agriculture is the main source of livelihood of the people of Assam. The Assamese people celebrate various festivals and social rituals focused on cultivations as they believe that it increases the fertility of the agricultural land, which results in the high productivity of crops. Just as a woman gives birth to a new life, a human being; similarly, the land on earth produces crops to sustain life of human beings. Logically both the earth and women are sources of fertile energy. Therefore, in Assamese society, both men and women involve in farming. It is also noticeable that because of sexual intercourse between a man and a woman, a child is born from the female womb; so various cultural activities emphasize the fertility of women; but premarital sexual intercourse between

men and women is not considered ethical in Hindu tradition..... Therefore, in Assamese society, men and women are given social recognition for sexual intercourse through marriage and then they can give birth to children.

II. Objective of the study

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- Determine the relationship between sexuality and Assamese culture.
- Determine the connection between religion and sexuality.
- To determine how sexuality is reflected in Assamese festivals and social behaviors.

III. Method of the study

The materials for this study have been collected by observing Assamese culture both directly and indirectly. Several Assamese books and the Internet have been used to analyze this topic.

IV. Discussion

Sexual attitudes are prevalent in folk cultures of every ethnic group in the world. Many cultural scholars consider sexual activities and behaviors of cultural elements as obscene; however, some other researchers suggest that the main cause of ancient religious rituals or magical beliefs were economic, not perverted sexual desire. Especially sexual beliefs related with cultivations have the objective of increasing crop production as the main source of people livelihood. Since in ancient times, sexually related cultural activities have had various magical thoughts. There is no shortage of magical rituals related with cultivation in the tribal groups of North East India. For example, *Malku (Myoko)* festival of *Apatani* tribe in Arunachal Pradesh, *sekrenya (sekrenyi)* festival of *Angami* tribe, *Wangala* and *Rongchugala* festival of *Garo* tribe, *Baisagu* festival of *Bodo* tribe, *Ali-Aye-Ligang* festival of *Mising* tribe etc.

Sexual thoughts and activities Related to Cultivations

In Indian tradition, many sexual beliefs have been associated with cultivations. Since land produces plants, foods etc. just like a woman produces children, so the earth has been compared to a woman. In Indian culture, the earth is considered to be a goddess and known by the title *Vasumati*, *Dharitri* etc. The Assamese people celebrate '*Bohag Bihu*' in the month of April just before they start farming and during this occasion people dance and sing in the fields and under the trees wishing for the increase in the fertility of the cultivation land i.e the earth. According to Hindu belief, the earth menstruates just like a woman does. This belief (which called *Sath Laga*, *Amti laga*) is observed in the Assamese month namely *Ahar* (month of Jun-July) and at this time the Assamese people do not work in farming land. In Assamese society,

a lady who is menstruating is not allowed to work during her menstrual period; Assamese farmers observe the same prohibition and give rest to the earth during those days and do not pluck anything from trees. The *Rabhas*, one of the ethnic groups of Assam, worship the goddess of agriculture by making a *mandap* (Small foundation of Soil), placing a piece of stone in the shape of women vagina on it and people use to dance all the night.¹ In the beginning of rice cultivation, Assamese people plant the wild cardamom trees (*Tora Gos*), the Taro plant (*Kosu Gos*), branches of Guava tree (*Modhuri Gosor Dal*) etc. in the cultivation land (*Pothar, a cornfield*) and worship with areca nut and betel leaf (*tamul-pan*) to the goddess of crops. They pray the goddess to grow the paddy just like the Taro plant and Guava as these plants grow rapidly in large amount. In Assam, women are allowed to plant paddy in the field and men hold the plough. Again, ploughing is done with bullock, not cows. The bull is a symbol of male reproductive fluid and the cow is a symbol of the *Basumata* (Earth).² The *Orang Community* of tea tribe of the Assam celebrates '*Karam Puja*' during *Kati Bihu* (national festival of Assam). Women play a major role in this festival. This festival is also related with fertility faith.

Sexual behaviors Related to Customs of Marriage

In Assamese society, there is a ceremony when a girl gets her first menstrual period. This ceremony is called as *small wedding* (or *Xanti Bia/Tuloni Bia/Xoru Bia* in Assamese). In this ceremony, the girl is bathed under a banana tree. They believe that this will make her fertile as banana tree. From the time of menstruation, a girl is ready to have sexual intercourse with a man and can give birth. Therefore, in the '*Xanti Biya*' ceremony, the menstruating girl is informed of these aspects by performing various rituals. In areas like Kamrup in Lower Assam, a menstruating girl is allowed to stay in an isolated room with a basket of paddy (*edoon dhan*) and a cluster of banana (*ethook kol*) nearby. Paddy and banana trees have high fertility. They do this in the belief that she can conceive and give birth in the future. On the third day of the girl's menstruation, *akhoi* (parched corn) is fried in her name. It is believed that if the *akhoi* is round shape, she will give birth to a baby boy in the future and if the *akhoi* is flat shape, she will give birth to a baby girl.

Marriage between a man and a woman begins their marital life. There are many rituals performed by the Assamese people during marriage ceremony to wish to have children. For example, giving fish in *Jurun* (the day when the ornaments, clothing etc. sent from the house of bridegroom to bride at the commencement of a marriage), planting twin banana trees in the

¹ Sivanath Barman, *Lokakristir Utcha*, p.45

² *ibid*, p.41

bride and groom's house, giving eggs the bride and groom to eat etc. This is because fish, eggs etc. are considered as symbol of fertility and it is believed that if they do so, the newly married bride-groom will have children soon. In a traditional Hindu wedding, *ranga sendur* (red vermilion) is given on the bride's forehead. According to the Assamese author Hem Barua, red is a symbol of sexual desire and sexuality.³

Sexuality expressed in religious things

Since ancient times, various religious activities and thoughts have reflected the view of sexuality. After the realization that children were born through sexual intercourse, which provided physical and mental pleasure, the *Yoni Puja Protha* (customs of worshipping the female genitals) began. *Yoni Puja* (Vagina worship) was first started because women used their vaginas to become pregnant and give birth. Later, *Linga Puja* (worship of Male sex organ) began. For a long time, Hindu people have placed a higher value on worshipping *Lingas* and *Yonis*. Hindus do *Linga Puja* to worship Lord *Shiva*, and *Yoni Puja* to worship goddess *Parvati or Sakti*. Shiva temples in Assam tend to worship *Lingas* rather than *Murtis* (idols, statue etc.). There is no idol in the *Kamakhya Temple* in Guwahati, Assam; instead, there is only a *Yoni akaror xil* (vaginal shape stone) on its *Bedi* (altar), through which water flow. Similarly, the idols in the *Siva dol* in Sivasagar, Assam are characterized by the position of the *Linga* and *Yoni* (the vagina) on the same stone.⁴ In Hindu religion, things like *Podum phool* (lotus flowers), *Bel Pat* (wood-apple leaves), ashoka flowers, triangular *Mandaps*, and *Trishul* (trident) are thought to represent the female genitalia. Similarly, *Purnaghatak* (the full pot) used in *Durga Puja* symbolizes the female womb.

According to general myth, goddesses go through their periods just like women do. Since *Maa Kamakhya* is thought to be menstruating during the Assamese month of *Ahar*, so the *Kamakhya Temple*, Assam is closed and no worship is performed. This ritual is celebrated only in Assam which is known as *Ambubachi*.

In ancient times, sexual intercourse was happened in most of the temples. This can be related to the *Devadasi Pratha* (*Devadasi customs*). '*Devadasi*'s were found especially in the temples of South India. According to *Devadasi customs*, a virgin girl is offered to a god in the temple according to the wish of her parents. Then that girl doesn't get married and instead referred to as a prostitute (*gonika*) of the god. On the other hand, a girl can have sex with any man.⁵ *Devadasi or Natini* were also found in the temples of Assam in ancient times.

³ *ibid*, p.47

⁴ *ibid*, p.28

⁵ Banikanta Kakati, *Purani Kamrupar Dharma Dhara*, *Banikanta Rachanawali*, P.182

Sexuality reflected in festivals

There are three national festivals of Assam: *Bohag Bihu* or *Rongali Bihu*, *Magh Bihu* or *Bhogali Bihu* and *Kati Bihu* or *Kongali Bihu*. The Bihu dance connected to the *Rangali Bihu* in Assam contains a lot of sexual intent. In this *Bihu*, the young boys and girls dancing and singing under the trees or in the middle of the fields in order to increase the fertility of the land. It is usual for young boys and girls to find their life partners while dancing *Bihu Nach* during this festival. At night, when young boys and girls celebrate *Bihu* by singing and dancing (*huchari mare*), they feel sexual interaction to each other; as a result, they choose a life partner and start their married life. The *Bihu* song (*Bihu Geet*) reflects the love and sexual thoughts of the young boys and girls that they feel for each other and also the desire for sexual intercourse between them. For Example:

Sit khai pariba hesa mari dhariba
Premare agote pari
Sarir udangai saba oi Lahori
*Gat goba mari dhari*⁶

(You will fall down, you will be pressed me, will fall in your love. Oh Dear,
 Holding my body out in front of you)

Many times, the movements of the body parts during the *Bihu dance* arouse feelings of lust towards the opposite sex. In spring (*Basanta ritu*), nature becomes rich in fruits and flowers and the crazy environment of nature awakens the minds of people. This joy also brings the desires. During *bihu* dance, to see the attractive body of young boys, throb of muscles; girl dancers (*Nachoni*) feel the sexual desire. And when the girls dance, the boys notice their trembling breast, which seduce them. In *Bihu* festival Assamese people play *Koni Zuj* (a game in which people hit on each other chicken or duck eggs keeping in their hands and determine the winner), *Kori Zuj* (a game played with the Cowrie shells). Both *Koni* (eggs) and *Kori* (Cowrie shell) are symbols of fertility. In '*Bhatheli*' festival celebrated in the Kamrup region, '*Paura Tola*' and '*Dahar Furua*' celebrated in the Bajali region, Assam; people decorated a long bamboo tree with colored cloths and perform procession. Bamboo tree is said to be a symbol of *Linga* (male sex organ). A festival '*Bax puja*' celebrated in Goalapara reflects the idea of reproduction, the genitals, various aspects of sexual activity etc. Many sexually intended songs are sung during this festival.

⁶ Upen Rabha Hakacham, *Bar Asomor Bihu Sanskriti*, P.315

V. Conclusion

There is an inseparable relationship between sexuality and Assamese culture. The Assamese people celebrate sexual rituals in recognition of the importance of the fertility of human being and the fertility of the earth's land. However, sexual related rituals are changing over the time. Under the influence of modernity, some ancient customs are gradually being abandoned or the importance of some sexual related beliefs has declined due to the changes bring about by the invention of science and technology. Despite this, some activities or behaviors related to sexuality are more welcomed by the society than ever before. Due to its sexual content, *Bihu dances* and *bihu songs* used to be considered as obscene, but this attitude has now changed. For example, now a days *Assomiya Bihu nach* (Assamese Bihu dance) is spreading all over the world. Now *Bihu Nach* and *Bihu geet* are accepted as a national identity of Assamese people. Everything in this world has both negative and positive aspect. So in this study we went through these aspects and express the thoughts related to Assamese culture and society. This study covers a vast area and our analysis reflects only a few sides of Assamese culture. In the future, in-depth research on this field can bring various informations.

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